

Proposed Law #121: A Law Opening All Public-School Classrooms as Temporary Shelters for Filipinos Living in High-Risk Areas

Version 1.0

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17567569

Date Written: November 9, 2025

"It is better to be prepared for an opportunity and not have one, than to have an opportunity and not be prepared." - Whitney Young

The same principle can be applied in natural calamities:

"It is better to be prepared for the worst-case scenario and not have one, than to be in a worst-case scenario and not be prepared."

Important Provisions:

All Filipinos living in high-risk areas may stay in public school classrooms at least one day before and after a natural calamity such as a typhoon.

High-risk areas include:

1. Areas near rivers or bodies of water
2. Mountainous areas or at the foot of mountains
3. Areas that were once rivers or bodies of water

Requirements:

Each classroom must have two accountable persons. One public official and one head of a family.

Proper documentation is required.

Both must take a picture and/or video of the classroom before the family stays there to ensure accountability.

The public official shall be the sole keeper of the classroom key, and one official may be in charge of up to 20 classrooms.

I understand that some cities and municipalities already have designated evacuation centers. However, many areas still lack such facilities.

Cebu could have reduced the number of casualties: 188 deaths and 135 missing, if the government had opened existing public infrastructures as temporary shelters.

Additional Provisions:

1. All public vehicles, including those of different local departments, shall be used to transport families from high-risk areas to public schools.

All private buses can also be used as vehicle.

The fuel costs shall be charged to the Local Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (LDRRM) budget.

2. The Reserve Armed Forces of the Philippines shall assist in transporting families, especially those in remote or mountainous areas.

Some Filipinos are not even aware when a Level 5 typhoon is approaching, so the Reserve Forces must locate and assist these families promptly.

Goal:

Zero Casualty and Zero Missing Filipinos After Every Typhoon

This proposed law may be implemented as a Presidential Executive Order or a local ordinance.

Due to the limited evacuation time in some high-risk areas, local governments are encouraged to implement the above measures in the next four to five hours.

"To all Mayors and Governors:

You have all the power and resources to save the lives of many important Filipinos.

You cannot just apologize later, after the typhoon, because of the number of casualties. You have to act now."

Note: *This document presents a core idea and does not yet constitute a fully drafted proposed law with detailed sections. It is intended as a foundation for further development and refinement in future legislative work.*

The majority of the first 100 Proposed Laws are included in The Great Nation 2025 started on December 9, 2024. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5310407> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5310407>).

Additional proposed laws will be gradually added in future updates.